

Supplemental Information

Multilayer double emulsion encapsulation of *Limosilactobacillus reuteri* using pectin-protein systems

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Table S1. Effect of Span 80: Tween 80 ratio on Lr/O emulsion stability.

Span 80:Tween 80	HLB	Creaming index (%)	Droplet size (μm)
3.75: 1.25	7.0	33.67 ± 5.98 ^{bc}	32.11 ± 2.16 ^c
4: 1	6.4	10.60 ± 4.28 ^a	27.42 ± 0.91 ^a
4.25: 0.75	5.9	28.27 ± 4.69 ^b	28.94 ± 2.57 ^b
4.5: 0.5	5.4	38.20 ± 2.27 ^{cd}	29.92 ± 1.37 ^b
4.75: 0.25	4.8	41.53 ± 5.48 ^d	33.83 ± 1.87 ^d

All values are mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates.

Different lowercase letters in the same column indicate significant differences between treatments ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure S1. Effect of Lr/O:W₂ ratio on the stability of Lr/O/W₂ double emulsion. a) Size distributions, b) size (d_{43}), and c) Creaming index.

Figure S2. Determination of the emulsifier saturation concentration (W_2) in the double emulsion ($W_1/O/W_2$): a) sodium caseinate, b) whey protein isolate, and c) saturation concentration of the pectin coating on the double emulsion.

Figure S3. Determination of the pH of maximum surface charge difference between: a) Cas-Pec and b) WPI-Pec.